

Chemical Examination of the Roots of *Aristolochia Indica*, Linn. Part I.

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Aristolochia indica (Sanskrit, *Rudrajata*; Kannada *Ishwari beru*) is a twining perennial plant growing all over the tropical portions of India. The roots taste very bitter and possess a characteristic aromatic odour. The root and the juice of the fresh leaves are said to be valuable antidotes to the bites of snakes and poisonous insects (Kanny Lall Dey, 'The Indigenous Drugs of India,' 1896, p. 36; Nadkarni, 'The Indian Materia Medica,' 1927, p. 83; Chopra, 'Indigenous Drugs of India,' 1933, p. 566). However, recently Mhaskar and Caius (*Indian Med. Res. Mem.*, 1931, No. 19, pp. 6, 19) have found that according to the technique employed by them, the plant has no antidotal or therapeutic effect against cobra venom.

The isolation of a bitter toxic substance, Serpentarin, from *A. serpentaria* by Chevallier, and a similar one Clemantitin, from *A. clemantitis* by Walz in 1853, may be noted among the earliest chemical studies in this family (Wehner, 'Die Pflanzenstoffe', 1931, Vol. I, p. 263). These were followed by those of Pohl on *A. rotunda* and *A. clemantitis*. He named the toxic substance Aristolochine and attributed to it the formula $C_{32}H_{22}O_{13}N_2$ (*Brit. Chem. Abs.*, 1892, 1, 874). Hesse (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1895, 233, 684) renamed this substance Aristolochic acid, on account of its acidic properties. Its formula was established as $C_{17}H_{11}O_7N$ by Castille (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1922, III, 272, 1301), who isolated it from *A. siphon*.

Hesse's work (*loc. cit.*) on the roots of *A. argentina* is of a more detailed character. From the alcoholic extract he was able to obtain in small quantities an amorphous alkaloid to which he reserved the name aristolochine. He was, however, unable to obtain it in a chemically pure form.

Further, from the ethereal extract of the roots he isolated three acids by making use of the differences in the solubility of their potassium salts in concentrated potassium hydroxide: aristinic acid, the principal constituent (m.p. 275° ; $C_{18}H_{13}O_7N$), aristidinic acid, an isomeric acid containing a methoxyl group (m.p. 260°) and aristolic acid (m.p., $260-70^\circ$; $C_{15}H_{11}(O_7)N$). These three acids and aristolochic acid are all more or less yellow compounds

and give dark green solutions with warm concentrated sulphuric acid. This property was taken as indicating their structural relationship. According to Hesse, Serpentarian of Chevallier and Clementatin of Walz are probably identical with aristolochic acid, and aristidinic acid is its monomethyl ether.

In addition to these bitter substances several other compounds such as essential oils, sterols, tannins, etc., have been isolated from different members of the *Aristolochiaceae* (Wehmer, *loc. cit.*).

The only mention in the literature regarding the chemical study of *A. indica* is that of Dymock and Warden ("Pharmacographica Indica", 1893, Vol. III, p. 158). Their work was of a very preliminary character and they obtained indications of the presence of a basic substance and of a brown or yellow resin. Consequently the present investigation was undertaken in order to isolate the constituents and to compare them with those obtained from the other species.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preliminary investigation.—50 G. of the crushed roots were extracted successively with the following solvents for 24 hours and the extracts dried at 100°

Solvent.	Percentage of extract.
Petroleum ether (b.p. 40-50°)	2·7
Ether	0·9
Chloroform	1·0
Ethyl acetate	0·5
Ethyl alcohol	5·1
	10·2
Total extractable material, 10·2	

500 G. of the powdered roots were subjected to steam distillation and the essential oil content was found to be 0·5% . . . When tested with Prollius fluid indication of the presence of alkaloidal constituents was obtained. Quantitative estimation showed that it varied between 0·05 to 0·07 per cent. in different samples.* An aqueous extract of

* These values refer to the alkaloidal content of roots obtained from the southern Tamil districts. Those obtained locally round about Bangalore contained only traces.

the roots contained small amounts of starch and reducing sugars and no tannins could be detected.

75 Kg. of carefully picked roots were crushed in a disintegrator and extracted by percolating the material thrice with hot alcohol. The solvent was then distilled off and the concentrated extract was subjected to steam distillation. The volatile constituents came over as a pale yellow oil (130 g.) which had the characteristic odour of the roots. A detailed study of this oil forms the subject matter of the second part.

The semi-solid residue left in the flask was separated from the aqueous layer (A) by decanting off the latter. It was dissolved in alcohol when a small amount of white crystalline material (0.4 g.) separated out. The alcoholic solution was dried on 2 Kg. of the crushed roots and exhaustively extracted with solvents in the order mentioned in the preliminary investigation.

Identification of a phytosterolin.—The solid substance mentioned above was recrystallised several times from large volumes of alcohol when the melting-point rose up to 285-90°. It answered the colour reactions of phytosterols and gave an acetyl derivative melting at 162-63°. Its properties indicated that it was probably a glucoside of the type of ipuranol. When hydrolysed by heating with an amyl alcoholic solution of hydrochloric acid according to the method of Power and Salway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 404) a phytosterol, melting at 146°, was obtained. The sugar produced was capable of reducing Fehling's solution, but the quantity was insufficient for the preparation of an osazone.

*Aqueous layer Separated from the Semi-solid Residue left
after Steam Distillation.*

Isolation of an alkaloid aristolochine.—The aqueous layer tasted very bitter and was found to contain a portion of the alkaloidal constituents dissolved probably in the salt form. On the addition of 5% sodium carbonate the liquid became turbid and a small amount of resinous material also separated out. It was then completely extracted with chloroform.

The chloroform solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered and extracted with 1% HCl. The solution of the hydrochlorides was boiled with animal charcoal, filtered and the bases reprecipitated by the addition of sodium carbonate. They were again extracted with chloroform and converted into the hydrochlorides.

The aqueous solution was concentrated on a water-bath and finally in a vacuum desiccator. The material crystallised out in the form of a microcrystalline powder. This was filtered, recrystallised and dried at 100°, m. p. 268° (decomp.).

The base liberated from the purified hydrochloride could be readily recrystallised from toluene. After a few recrystallisations it melted with decomposition at 158-159°. However, when attempts were made to recrystallise the substance from methyl alcohol, it dissolved very readily but separated out after a few minutes. This material could then be crystallised only from a large volume of methyl alcohol, m.p. 215°. A similar conversion took place when the original alkaloid was dissolved in absolute alcohol. The substance decomposing at 158° appears to be a molecular compound of the alkaloid with toluene.

It is proposed to call this well-defined chemically individual alkaloid Aristolochine, the name applied to various substances isolated from different species of the *Aristolochiaceae* (Wehmer, *loc. cit.*, Hesse, *loc. cit.*). The complete characterisation of this alkaloid will form the subject of a subsequent communication.

Isolation of allantoin.—The aqueous layer after removal of the alkaloidal constituents was treated successively with lead acetate and basic lead acetate. The precipitates obtained were only in very small amounts. Excess of lead was then removed by passing in hydrogen sulphide and the liquid was concentrated under diminished pressure to half the volume.

It was then extracted with amyl alcohol. The amyl alcoholic extract was dried over sodium sulphate and concentrated under diminished pressure. A reddish syrup was obtained which possessed reducing properties. Attempts to isolate chemically individual substances from this proved a failure.

The aqueous solution was further concentrated and the residue obtained in the form of a thick syrup. Treatment of a portion of this with phenylhydrazine yielded glucosazone (m. p. 210°). The material contained hydrolysable sugars. But these could not be separated in a pure condition for purposes of identification.

The syrup was dissolved in absolute methyl alcohol and left in the ice-chest for a few days. A crop of large prismatic crystals separated out slowly. These were collected and crystallised from boiling water (charcoal) as colourless prisms, m. p. 232° (decomp.). (Found: C, 30.2; H, 3.9; N, 35.5. $C_4H_6N_4O_3$ requires C, 30.4; H, 3.8; N, 35.4 per cent). Its properties and analytical data indi-

cated that it was allantoin and the melting point was not depressed when mixed with a specimen of pure allantoin prepared from uric acid.

The Petroleum Ether Extract.

This extract consisted of a dark brown oil (1.25 kg.). After keeping it for some days a small quantity of phytosterolin (0.2 g.) separated and was found to be identical with the one already described.

Glycerol.—The oil was saponified and the crude fatty acids were liberated by the addition of dilute sulphuric acid to the soap solution. The aqueous layer was treated with barium carbonate and the filtered solution was concentrated to a small bulk on a water-bath under diminished pressure. The resulting syrup was identified as glycerol by the acrolein test.

The fatty acids were then converted to soap and the soap, sliced into thin shreds, was air-dried and extracted with ether to obtain the unsaponifiable matter. The fatty acids were liberated again and separated into their solid and liquid constituents by the Twitchell method (*J. Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806).

Oleic and linolic acids.—The liquid acids were converted into their methyl esters and the latter were purified by distillation at a pressure of 1 mm. The acids were again liberated and a portion of them was brominated according to the method of Eibner and Muggenthaler. Among the products formed there was no ether-insoluble substance and tetrabromstearic acid (m. p. 113.4°; M. W. 603.0) was isolated. Another portion of the acids was oxidised in alkaline solution by dilute permanganate. The crude mixture of hydroxy acids was washed with a little petroleum ether and then extracted with ether when dihydroxystearic acid (m. p. 131°; M. W. 314) was obtained. The residue was boiled with water and filtered. The acid which crystallised out on cooling proved to be tetrahydroxystearic acid (m. p. 158°; M. W. 347).

Palmitic, stearic, lignoceric and cerotic acids.—The methyl esters (300 g.) of the solid acids were carefully fractionated at 1 mm. pressure :

No. of fraction.	Temperature.	Wt. of the distillate.	Mean M. W. from saponification value.
1	154-164°	165 g.	258
2	164-170°	30	260
3	170-175°	20	270
4	175-182°	15	276
5	182-190°	20	314
Residue	...	50	...

Pure palmitic acid was obtained from the first two fractions (m. p. 62.0°; M. W. 256; m. p. of *p*-phenylphenacyl ester 93.4°). The acid liberated from fractions 3 and 4 after repeated crystallisations from alcohol proved to be stearic acid (m. p. 69°; M. W. 282; m. p. of *p*-phenyl-phenacyl ester 97.8°) and crude lignoceric acid was isolated from the 5th fraction (m. p. 75°; M. W. 368; m. p. of *p*-phenylphenacyl ester 101.2°).

The resinified residue in the flask was dissolved in alcohol, saponified and the dark-coloured acid that separated was dissolved in alcohol and boiled with animal charcoal for several hours. On filtering and cooling, a pale brown slimy material (1 g.) separated. This was filtered and recrystallised several times from alcohol when it came out as a colourless slime (m. p. 78°; M. W. 396). These properties indicate that it is cerotic acid.

Phytosterol and ceryl alcohol.—A reddish brown oil (400 g.) was obtained as the unsaponifiable matter. This had the characteristic odour of the roots and the presence of a small amount of the volatile oil was suspected. Consequently it was subjected to steam distillation. The essential oil was found to be very slightly volatile with steam (5 c. c. passed over with 3 litres of water), and hence the reddish brown oil was distilled in high vacuum and the distillate collected up to 180° was obtained as a pale green oil (90 g.). The residue in the flask solidified to a black mass.

The volatile oil was fractionated into two portions, one boiling at 104.5°/1 mm. (10 g.) and the other (70 g.) at 130.2°/1 mm. (For the chemical study of these, *vide* part II).

The black residue was repeatedly crystallised from boiling alcohol (charcoal) and finally 20 g. of a colourless crystalline material separated out, m. p. 137.8°. It answered the colour reactions of phytosterols and gave an acetyl derivative, m. p. 127°

From the alcoholic mother liquors about 0.5 g. of a colourless slimy material separated out after several days. This substance on several recrystallisations from alcohol melted at 79° (Found: C, 81.5; H, 14.0. Calc for $C_{26}H_{54}O$: C, 81.7; H, 14.2 per cent). Its acetyl derivative melted at 65°. These results indicate that it is ceryl alcohol.

The Ether Extract.

isoAristolochic acid.—As the extraction with ether proceeded a microcrystalline yellow solid separated out from the solvent. The

extraction was stopped after 48 hours although the liquid was still pale yellow in colour.

It could be crystallised from large volumes of alcohol or glacial acetic acid as yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 275° (decomp.), yield 10 g. [Found: C, 59.9; H, 3.4; N, 4.1; M. W. in nitrobenzene (ebullioscopic method) 322. $C_{17}H_{11}O_7N$ requires C, 59.8; H, 3.3; N, 4.1 per cent. and M. W. 341].

This bitter principle is similar to and isomeric with Aristolochic acid (m. p. 215°) isolated by various workers from different species of *Aristolochiaceae* (Webmer, *loc. cit.*) and consequently it has been named *isoaristolochic acid*.*

The acid is intensely bitter to taste and is very sparingly soluble in the usual organic solvents. The solutions in glacial acetic acid and alcohol show a feeble greenish fluorescence. It dissolves readily in pyridine (a brownish yellow solution) from which it is thrown down on acidification. It dissolves in ammonia, caustic alkalies, alkali carbonates and bicarbonates (dark red solutions). The sodium salt crystallised from water as a dark red powder containing a molecule of water of crystallisation, which is lost only above 150° . (Found: Na, 5.9. $C_{17}H_{10}O_7N \cdot Na, H_2O$ requires Na, 6.04 per cent).

The acid contains neither a methoxyl group (Zeisel) nor a methylenedioxy group (Hans Meyer, "Analyse und Konstitution-Ermittlung Organischer Verbindungen," 1931, p. 497; Sanchez and d' Alessio, *Chem. Zentral.*, 1932, 11, 257). No indications of the presence of an enolic group were obtained when the substance in alcoholic solution was tested with sodium nitroprusside or tetranitromethane. Estimation of active hydrogen atom was carried out according to the method of Zerewitinoff, suspending the substance in amyl ether. The material gradually formed a deep green solution, and the volume of the gas evolved remained constant after one hour and was equivalent to one active hydrogen atom.

The substance dissolved in boiling acetic anhydride and could be recovered unchanged after one hour. If the boiling was continued, the solution gradually assumed a black colour due to decomposition. No pure product could be isolated from the reaction mixtures. Attempts at acetylation according to several different methods have

* This substance was also found to occur in varying amounts in different samples of the roots. In one experiment 6 g. were obtained from 10 kg. of the roots, and in another 18 g. In the latter case, it is interesting to note that the alkaloid was present only in traces.

so far been unsuccessful. The acid does not react with hydroxylamine, phenylhydrazine or semicarbazide. Further, it has not been found possible to prepare a methiodide. The acid is unaffected when boiled with 50% potassium hydroxide (or 2%) methyl alcoholic potash for 3 hours. Alkali fusion, however, resulted in considerable resinification, and no definite results could be obtained. With concentrated sulphuric acid, it gives a dark green colouration which changes to brown after addition of a drop of concentrated nitric acid. It is unacted upon by boiling hydrochloric acid, either dilute or concentrated.

Benzoyl isoaristolochic acid.—Benzoylation was effected by the Schotten-Baumann method, using potassium hydroxide. Only a small quantity of the derivative separated from the alkaline solution and considerable difficulty was experienced in its purification. Yellow microcrystalline powder from xylene, m.p. 170-71° (decomp.). (Found: C, 64.9; H, 3.6; N, 3.0. $C_{24}H_{15}O_8N$ requires C, 64.7; H, 3.4; N, 3.2 per cent).

Methyl isoaristolochic acid, prepared in the usual manner with methyl sulphate (8 mols.), crystallised from ethyl benzoate in yellow needles, m.p. 267° (decomp.). (Found: C, 61.0; H, 3.8; N, 3.9; OMe, 9.1. $C_{18}H_{13}O_7N$ requires C, 60.9; H, 3.7; N, 3.9; OMe, 8.7 per cent).

The substance is quite tasteless and is unaffected when refluxed with *N*-methyl alcoholic potash for 4 hours. The product is thus an ether and it follows that *isoaristolochic acid* does not contain a carboxyl group.

Oxidation with hydrogen peroxide: Isolation of an acid of the formula $C_{16}H_{13}O_9N$.—2 G. of *iso* aristolochic acid dissolved in dilute caustic potash (6 g. in 700 c.c. of water) were treated with 9% hydrogen peroxide (31.2 g.) during half an hour at the laboratory temperature (25°). The oxidation was allowed to proceed for 3 hours, with occasional stirring. The excess of hydrogen peroxide was destroyed on the water-bath (1 hour) and the cooled solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid, filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to one-third the volume. When the concentrated solution was kept in the ice chest for 18 hours, a slightly reddish solid separated. This was washed with cold water to remove the colouring matter and then repeatedly crystallised from boiling water, when it was obtained as colourless, short, hairy, needles, m.p., 164.5°. [Found: C, 52.0; H, 3.7; N, 3.9; and Eq. wt., 181. $C_{14}H_{11}O_5N(COOH)_2$ requires C, 52.9; H, 3.6; N, 3.9 per cent. and Eq. wt., 182]. It lost 1 molecule of water when kept at 120° for 3 hours.

Further experiments on the constitution of isoaristolochic acid are in progress and the results will be communicated in a subsequent paper.

Though Hesse (*loc. cit.*) has isolated three different acidic substances from the roots of *A. argentina*, no other substances similar to isoaristolochic acid could be obtained from the roots of *A. Indica*.

The ethereal solution left after filtering off the bitter principle was then extracted with 1% HCl. The amount of alkaloidal material thus obtained was very small and this acid extract was worked up along with the one obtained from the chloroform extract. The ether solution was next extracted with dilute Na_2CO_3 and a small amount of the bitter principle that had remained dissolved in ether was thus recovered. The ether solution was subsequently treated with dilute NaOH, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the ether distilled off. In this manner small amounts of acidic and neutral resinous bodies were obtained. Acid hydrolysis of these did not give any definite results.

The Chloroform Extract.

Here also the bitter principle separated out from solution as the extraction proceeded (13 g.). This was filtered off and washed with a little chloroform. The washings were added to the main extract. The chloroform solution was then extracted with 1% HCl. The hydrochloric acid solution was worked up in the manner described before and the alkaloid obtained here was identical with the one isolated from aqueous layer mentioned in p. 478. Subsequent extractions with Na_2CO_3 , gave some more of the dissolved bitter principle. Alkali took up the acidic resin and the neutral product obtained by distilling off chloroform was also found to be a resin. These were non-glucosidic in character.

The Ethyl Acetate Extract.

The bitter principle again separated out during the extraction (17 g.). The solution was distilled and a little more of the bitter principle was recovered. The residue was found to consist of a small amount of a thick reddish resinous material. When this material was boiled with dilute alcoholic hydrochloric acid a small quantity of the bitter principle separated out. Alcohol was distilled over and the neutralised aqueous solution was found to reduce Fehling's solution. Probably the resin contains a glucoside of the bitter principle but this could not be isolated.

The Final Alcoholic Extract.

On concentration and dilution with water a considerable quantity of semi-solid, greyish-black resin separated in an amorphous form. This was soluble in alcohol and alkalis and could be recovered only by reprecipitation. All attempts at its purification proved of no avail. Alkaline and acid hydrolyses were also attempted but without any definite results. The aqueous solution after removal of alcohol by distillation under diminished pressure was examined in the manner described under A. It contained a considerable amount of sugars and from these glucosazone was prepared (m.p. 208°). No glucosidic component could be detected.

SUMMARY.

As a result of the systematic analysis of the roots of *Aristolochia indica* the following substances have been found to occur in it.

1. An essential oil which is responsible for its characteristic odour. This oil consists mostly of high boiling constituents, and owing to its feeble volatility with steam the higher fractions are obtained in the unsaponifiable matter extracted by petroleum ether.

2. The fixed oil is made up of the glycerides of the palmitic, stearic, lignoceric, cerotic, oleic and linolic acids. A considerable amount of sitosterol, a small quantity of the glucoside of phytosterol melting at 146° and ceryl alcohol were isolated from the unsaponifiable matter.

3. The roots are found to contain a very bitter yellow compound sparingly soluble in most of the usual organic solvents. This has the formula $C_{17}H_{11}O_7N$ and is not identical with any of the compounds isolated from other species of *Aristolochiaceae*. It has been named *isoaristolochic acid*.

4. From the basic constituents *Aristolochine*, a new alkaloid, has been isolated as the principal component.

5. The roots have been found to contain considerable amount of reducing sugars from which glucosazone could be readily obtained. Along with these allantoin is found to occur and has been isolated in a pure condition.

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